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OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASI O'QITUVCHI KASSIYASINI ARTTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHARTLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada jamiyat taraqqiyotining hozirgi bosqichida O'zbekiston oliy ta'limini isloh qilish siyosati qo'ygan talablarga javob berish maqsadida universitet o'qituvchilarining malakasini oshirish muammosi ko'rib chiqiladi. O'qituvchilarning o'z faoliyatini isloh qilish uchun motivatsiyasini shakllantirish va kasbiy rivojlanish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlarni yaratish zarurligi asoslanadi. Bundan tashqari oliy ta'lim o'qituvchilarini malakasini oshirishda kelib chiqadigan muammolarni ko'rib chiqqan holda har tomonlama qo'llab quvvatlash, kerakli chora tadbirlarni ko'rib chiqish nazarda tutiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: universitet o'qituvchisi, malaka oshirish, pedagogik shart-sharoitlar, motivatsiya, maqsadni belgilash, aks ettirish, mulohazalar, natijalar diagnostikasi.

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ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЯ ВУЗА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается проблема повышения квалификации преподавателей вузов с целью соответствия требованиям, предъявляемым политикой реформирования узбекской высшей школы на современном этапе развития общества. Обосновывается необходимость формирования мотивации педагогов к реформированию собственной деятельности и создания определенных педагогических условий, способствующих профессиональному развитию. Кроме того, планируется оказать всестороннюю поддержку и рассмотреть необходимые меры по повышению квалификации преподавателей высшей школы.

Ключевые слова: преподаватель вуза, профессиональное развитие, педагогические условия, мотивация, целеполагание, рефлексия, обратная связь, диагностика результатов

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PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT TEACHER

ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problem of professional development of university teachers in order to meet the requirements imposed by the policy of reforming Uzbek higher education at the present stage of development of society. The necessity of formation of motivation of teachers to reform their own activities and the creation of certain pedagogical conditions conducive to professional development is substantiated. In addition, it is planned to provide comprehensive support and consider the necessary measures to improve the skills of higher education teachers.

Keywords: university teacher, professional development, pedagogical conditions, motivation, goal setting, reflection, feedback, diagnostics of results.

The reform of education, regardless of the implementation mechanisms – changes in educational standards, restructuring of educational institutions, redistribution of hours allocated to the study of disciplines, etc. – is initiated in order to obtain the result most appropriate to the social and economic conditions of the functioning of the state in a certain historical period. In other words, the reform involves obtaining a qualitatively different graduate of the educational program of a school or university with a set of knowledge and competencies that meet the needs of the labor market. However, despite the considerable efforts made by administrators and performers of different levels, as well as significant financial costs for retraining teachers, buying expensive equipment and methodological support, little changes in the methods and methods of interaction between teachers and students in school classrooms and university classrooms.

Describing the state of modern university education, L.F. Vyaznikova notes the presence of a paradox, which consists in the fact that educational institutions, the content of academic subjects (disciplines) and the forms of their teaching are changing, but the pedagogical attitude itself remains unchanged for many teachers, its identification matrix, although the participants in the educational process create the illusion of changes. Significant for society, in her opinion, is the socio-cultural function of education, namely, the socialization of the individual, the transfer of social experience. In practice, "most teachers are focused on the objective (material) reality – knowledge, on a completely structured "model" of a specialist, ignoring the subjective reality of a person who knows" [1, 59].

Back in the 20s of the last century, L.S. Vygotsky wrote that where a teacher acts as a "simple pump pumping a student with knowledge, he can successfully be replaced by a textbook, dictionary, map, excursion... It's time to put the student on his own feet, make him walk and fall, endure the pain of bruises and choose a direction" [2, 387]. At the same time, the famous scientist emphasized that in order to give direction to the student to develop, the teacher himself must be a highly developed person and know much more ("a hundred times more") what he has to give.

It is impossible to create conditions under which a student would be perceived as an equal subject of the educational process, and to obtain a qualitatively new educational result in the form of a competent competitive graduate without "reforming" the teacher. You can equip every school office or university auditorium with multimedia whiteboards, computers with high-speed Internet access, train teachers to work with new equipment and not get the desired result. The teacher, in the presence of colleagues or the commission, will demonstrate the capabilities of the technique and the new methodology, and in the absence of inspectors, he will return to his usual monotonous presentation of the material memorized over many years of practice. Or, as it happens, he will "entrust" all training to the computer, sending students to arbitrary navigation through the vast expanses of the "world wide

Web" throughout the entire lesson. And who can blame him for the fact that expensive equipment is not used during the lesson? However, both in the first and in the second case it will be difficult to get the result for which the reform was started. The teacher, due to his own limitations, which L.S. Vygotsky spoke about, simply does not realize the problems, as a result, does not see the need for changes or, for a number of reasons, is not motivated to change in his professional activity.

There are different views on ways to increase teachers' motivation to reform their own activities:

- increasing the level of remuneration of teachers to stimulate the introduction of innovations;
- organization of training on working with new equipment and training technologies through advanced training courses;
- implementation of a quality management system with strict reporting in accordance with approved standards, etc.

All of the above methods undoubtedly motivate teachers to change their work with a focus on obtaining the desired learning outcomes, but this type of motivation has an external character. As for internal motivation, describing the motives for performing pedagogical activities, teachers and psychologists talk about the motive of power, focused on helping others through knowledge. At the same time, assistance can be understood as any actions aimed at the well-being of other people, which is consonant with the humanistic interpretation of the motivation of learning [3]. Internal motivation helps the teacher to achieve high results even in the absence of external motivation.

The conscious movement towards more successful indicators in pedagogical activity is determined by the need for professional development, which is realized when the following pedagogical conditions are met:

1. teachers' awareness of the need for change;
2. availability of resources and readiness of the administration to support the initiative of teachers;
3. goal setting and choosing a professional development model;
4. organization of feedback and support in case of difficulties;
5. availability of methods for diagnosing the results of professional development.

Let's take a closer look at each of the conditions.

1. Teachers' awareness of the need for change. According to A. Underhill, the professional development of a teacher can be considered as a movement from "unconscious incompetence" (the teacher does not see difficulties, does not understand that he is doing something wrong) to "unconscious/ automatic competence" (the teacher is so competent that, without thinking, easily and successfully copes with professional tasks) [5, 76].

In order for the desire to achieve a high level of professionalism to appear, the teacher needs to realize the problem, namely the lack of his own knowledge, skills, and take measures to solve it. In understanding the need to change the professional activity of a teacher, the results of students' academic performance, the study of normative documents, reading methodological literature, questionnaires for assessing the difficulties of their own activities, questionnaires for evaluating the activity of a teacher by students, attending classes of colleagues, scientific and methodological seminars and conferences can help.

In the modern educational process, it is important for a teacher to understand the trends of its development, namely:

- shifting the focus of pedagogical attention from the educational material to the personality of the student;
- availability of modern educational technologies that provide a variety of tools and methods that contribute to the realization of goals and objectives, both individual courses and personal goals of students;
- changing the educational context, which consists in bringing it closer to real professional situations, as well as filling it with personal meaning for each student.

The transition to the educational standards of the third generation in the system of higher education involves the organization of training on the principles of competence-activity approach, which entails a change in the content and forms of work.

Traditional lectures with "reading" information and seminars with "reproducing" the material told by the teacher should give way to full-fledged intersubjective communication. It also requires teachers to review their own activities and introduce active forms of learning.

2. As for the second condition, the effectiveness of the professional development of teachers largely depends on the resource base of the university (developed infrastructure, personnel and information support) And also on the importance attached to this development by the administration of the educational institution in which the teachers work. If the administration does not create conditions for teachers under which everyone has the opportunity to achieve success that gives confidence in their own abilities and abilities, then the need for professional development disappears, the willingness of the administration to support the initiative, organize training, invite specialists, buy the necessary training tools, help with postgraduate studies, internships, publications, etc., contributes to the creation of an environment, favorable for professional growth.

Speaking about the administration, it is necessary to take into account all its levels, since it happens that conditions for development have been created in an educational institution as a whole, and at the unit level the head is not interested in the growth of colleagues, seeing this as undesirable competition and a threat to his position as a leader. Such a leader, in order not to get out of the context of the entire organization, can declare development, which in fact will turn out to be nothing more than an ISA – imitation of stormy activity. Any initiative coming from a teacher will directly intersect under various pretexts or indirectly switch to solving any urgent problems.

Undoubtedly, in order to support his subordinates in the desire to grow professionally, the leader himself should not stop at what has been achieved, but justify his position as a leader with real achievements. Such a position will not only provide the necessary conditions for development, but will also serve as a role model, motivating teachers to learn new things for the benefit of professional activity.

The teacher, in turn, needs to understand that his interests should not conflict with the interests of the development of the organization in which he or she works, and should not require support in the development of those skills and abilities that are not consistent with his or her immediate job responsibilities and specialization of the discipline taught.

3. Goal-setting in education determines the logic of its development. Being a component of the education system, the goal gives consistency to the teacher's activities. It determines the content, nature and dynamics of professional development, as well as selects tools and methods.

Goal-setting by its nature is based on the action of the mechanism of reflexive self-assessment concerning successes and failures in the past, as well as difficulties experienced in current activities. Therefore, the setting of goals is influenced by the fact that the teacher has an established and developing professional work experience, possesses specific techniques, skills and abilities, carries out self-analysis and self-assessment of educational and professional activities. Being the subject of goal-setting in professional development, the teacher proceeds from his own needs and abilities, as well as learning strategies formed on the basis of past experience. Subjectivity puts the teacher in the position of a person responsible for his achievements, since the self-affirmation of a person as a person is directly related to a change in the effectiveness of behavior in the process of achieving results, which is possible only if a person feels controlled by what he is doing and considers the result of his action dependent on his own efforts. The success of professional development increases if the teacher has freedom of choice in ways to achieve the goal.

As for the choice of a professional development model, then, in accordance with the goals, individual preferences and employment, the teacher can choose both intensive and extensive in time, on-the-job or on-the-job, individual or group forms of training, research, advanced training, etc.

4. The presence of feedback in the process of professional development of the teacher allows you to solve two tasks: to provide assistance in case of difficulties and to measure achievements. In the first case, through a questionnaire, a conversation or a reflexive assessment of the past seminar, training, refresher course, etc., the coach, methodologist or organizer can get the necessary information about the compliance of the training with the expectations of students, the relevance of the content to the learning objectives, difficulties encountered during the performance of tasks.

Flexibility in the approach to changes in training in accordance with the needs of students and timely assistance in case of difficulties greatly contribute to maintaining motivation for the process of professional development. The teacher develops an understanding of the significance of what he is doing and a sense of confidence in achieving success.

Pedagogical reflection, which is considered to be an integral component of professional and pedagogical skills, influencing the development of professional competence, is especially important for assessing one's successes and failures. Researchers agree that the ability to reflect helps a teacher to find an individual style of professional activity, allows to achieve adequate professional and personal self-esteem, predict and analyze the results of their activities, increases the level of self-organization.

5. It is well known that in the educational process, the student's attitude to the goal / result is largely formed under the influence of control and evaluation. Professional development should be measurable. Of course, it is difficult to simultaneously measure the formation of such professional competencies as, for example, "readiness for systematization, generalization and dissemination of methodological experience (domestic and foreign) in the professional field" or "the ability to form an educational environment and use their abilities in implementing the tasks of innovative educational policy" [4,6]. Such competencies are manifested throughout the entire professional activity. However, much can and should be measured to properly understand where the teacher is relative to his colleagues and how the new results relate to previous own. Advanced training courses, as a rule, end with graduation papers, for which certificates of successful completion are issued, passing international exams (in the case of foreign language teachers) with a certificate confirms the level of subject competence, research work in graduate school ends with the defense of a dissertation with a diploma, further research is reflected in the number and quality of publications. The direct results of a teacher's professional development can be observed by colleagues while attending classes or master classes conducted by him, indirectly through the achievements of his trainees.

Twice a year, university teachers report to the department on the results of their work in the semester, filling out individual plans with quantitative indicators of the results of their activities. The university administration can set its own criteria for evaluating the activities of departments, also quantifying the results of events, publications, dissertations, volumes of research works, and other indicators.

For a qualitative assessment of the teacher's activity, scientists have proposed various methods according to the criteria for evaluating the teaching activity, the functional aspect of the activity, personality traits, etc. In secondary schools, various forms of introspection are used, considering different indicators of the teacher's activity.

The most fully reflecting the dynamics of the teacher's development, in our opinion, is the management of a portfolio, as a special systematic collection of documents and other relevant information, acting as a way of reflexive assessment of one's own activities and presentation of its results to confirm the formation of professional competencies.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that reforming education, including higher education, among other significant components, significantly depends on how motivated teachers are to become subjects of changing their own activities. The formation of internal motivation is possible through the professional development of a university teacher, implemented when creating certain pedagogical conditions, namely: diagnostic tools for problems, support for the university administration, goal setting and flexibility in offering models of professional development and types of feedback, as well as methods for evaluating achievements.

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